

FORECASTING ENROLLMENT IN THE TERTIARY LEVEL USING POLYNOMIAL REGRESSION

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Abstract. This study looks into the historical data on enrollment from the Registrar's Office starting from S.Y. 2019-2020 to 2023-2024. It covers a number of enrollees from all tertiary-level programs at the beginning of each school year. The data were plotted and trendlines were added to have a glimpse of a possible number of enrollees in the school year 2024-2025. A polynomial regression was used to forecast the said data. A promising outlook on enrollment for the next school year was seen and can be a basis for strategic planning.

Keywords. Forecast, Enrollment, Polynomial Regression

1 Introduction

Forecasting is the process of using historical data, current trends, and expert opinions to predict future events or outcomes. Forecasting is essential for the academe, as it helps researchers, educators, and administrators to plan, evaluate, and improve their activities and programs. By forecasting, the academe can anticipate the needs and expectations of their stakeholders, such as students, faculty, staff, administration, and the community. Forecasting can also support the decision-making process in the academe, by providing evidence-based information and insights that can guide the selection and implementation of the best courses of action the process of using historical data, current trends, and expert opinions to predict future events or outcomes.

Hossler and Shapiro (2019) contribute to the literature with their work on "Strategic Enrollment Management." The book explores transformative practices in higher education, emphasizing the strategic role of forecasting in enrollment management. The authors highlight the importance of aligning institutional goals with enrollment projections to make informed decisions that contribute to the overall success of the institution.

Kim and Shin (2020) present a forecasting model specifically tailored for university enrollment management. Their research delves into the intricacies of forecasting in higher education, providing a nuanced approach to address the challenges institutions face in predicting and managing student enrollment, which is essential for resource allocation and program planning.

Lee and Kang (2021) offer insights into the use of predictive analytics for student success in higher education. The systematic literature review explores how forecasting, coupled with advanced analytics, contributes to identifying factors influencing student success. The study emphasizes the role of forecasting in designing interventions that support student retention and academic achievement.

Sengupta and Biswas (2019) present a case study focusing on financial forecasting in higher education. The research highlights the critical role of forecasting in financial planning, aiding institutions in making informed decisions related to budgeting and resource allocation, especially in an era of economic uncertainties.

Wiers-Jenssen and Naevestad (2019) contribute to the literature by comparing statistical models for student enrollment forecasting. Their study provides insights into the effectiveness of different forecasting approaches, guiding academic institutions in choosing suitable models to project student enrollments accurately and enhance decision-making in areas such as class scheduling and resource allocation.

Forecasting is essential for the academe, as it helps researchers, educators, and administrators to plan, evaluate, and improve their activities and programs. By forecasting, the academe can anticipate the needs and expectations of its stakeholders, such as students, faculty, staff, funders, and society. Forecasting can also support the in the academe, by

providing evidence-based information and insights that can guide the selection and implementation of the best courses of action. In recent years, the academic landscape has witnessed a surge in the importance of forecasting as an indispensable tool for decision-making support.

San Carlos College is not exempted. As an institution that believes in data and the possible forecast based on historical data, it is imperative to embrace its outcomes use it in top-level decision-making, and consider it as an asset.

2 Research Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive-developmental method of research. Enrollment data from S.Y. 2019-2020 to S.Y. 2023-2024 of the different programs at the tertiary level was gathered from the Registrar's Office through the Registrar, Annjannette T. Macadangang. The data was categorized by semesters and by program. The earning units were not included in the analysis since the seasonality cannot be determined. Additionally, only the first semester was included in this study. The attrition rate can be written in a separate paper.

Analysis per program was done using a polynomial regression utilizing the coefficient of determination (R-squared). R-squared (R^2) is a statistical measure that represents the proportion of the variance for a dependent variable that's explained by an independent variable in a regression model. In formula:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\text{Unexplained variation}}{\text{Total variation}}$$

R-squared values range from 0 to 1. An R-squared value of 0 means that the model explains or predicts 0% of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. A value of 1 indicates that the model predicts 100% of the relationship, and a value of 0.5 indicates that the model predicts 50%, and so on.

The forecasting was made using a spreadsheet application. To visualize the pattern from the data, a Scatter Plot with smooth lines and markers is used. The red dashed line represents the trend based on the historical data.

3 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

Enrollment data for different programs in the tertiary level for the first semester from School Year 2019-2020 to 2023-2024 were gathered from the Registrar's Office. The table shows the enrollment data:

Table 1. Enrollment Data of Tertiary Programs from S.Y. 2019-2020 to 2023-2024

Programs	School Years				
	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024
BSA	199	154	155	171	211
BSBA	41	38	59	41	63
BSIT	50	52	78	92	129
BSCrim	0	4	15	54	125
BSEd	140	104	113	73	103
BEEd	36	32	33	25	36
MAEd	54	17	29	10	23
Total	520	401	482	466	690

The BS in Accountancy program has seen a decrease in enrollment starting in S.Y. 2020-2021 with 154 enrollees. This may be attributed to the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic. But as the pandemic subsides, a slow but steady increase can be seen starting S.Y. 2021-2022. However, it can be seen that only during 2023 that enrollment has regained its number since 2019. Using the R-squared function, it forecasted having 280+ students on the S.Y. 2024-2025 with 97.35% confidence in the relations between variables (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Enrollment Forecast for BSA for the S.Y. 2024-2025

The BS in Business Administration has an unusual plot as seen in Figure 2. A small downward trend during the COVID-19 pandemic can be seen in 2020-2021, suddenly increasing and a big fall in the following year. However, the forecast for the enrollment for BSBA has a bit increase coming next school year around 68 students.

Figure 2. Enrollment Forecast for BSBA for the S.Y. 2024-2025

The BS in Information Technology program has a constant and steady progress despite the COVID-19 pandemic. It started with a slow increase and gained momentum as years passed by. Using the R-squared function, a forecast of 164 students may be seen in the next school year at a 98.3% percentage of correlation (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Enrollment Forecast for BSIT for the S.Y. 2024-2025

Started right after the pandemic, the BS in Criminology started to entertain enrollees. Being the youngest college, the program is the cream of the crop these years. Having 125 students in the first semester of S.Y. 2023-2024, the college hopes to have at least 200 enrollees in the next school year at 99.39% confidence (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Enrollment Forecast for BSCrim for the S.Y. 2024-2025

The BS in Secondary Education program experienced a swerving up-and-down trend. Although there was an increase in enrollment in S.Y. 2021-2022, a large 35% decrease followed, from 113 to 73. It almost regained its number in 2023. Hoping, that if the uptrend continues, a small increase can be expected not unless caught again in the swerving pattern (Figure 5). The program hasn't regained its original number in 2019. It is still down by 26.4% compared to the latest enrollment data.

The Bachelor in Elementary Education program experienced almost the same situation as the BS in Secondary Education. It might have not the same drop as the BSEd in 2020 but the pattern is still the same. The BEEd is expected to have at least 41 students in the next school year. The program regained its number in 2019 and is now the same as the latest number.

Figure 5. Enrollment Forecast for BSEd for the S.Y. 2024-2025

Figure 6. Enrollment Forecast for BEd for the S.Y. 2024-2025

Sharing the same fate with BEd and BEEd in terms of enrollment is the Master in Education graduate program. It suffers a 68.5% drop in enrollment during the COVID-19 pandemic. Although it recovered in 2021, it immediately dropped to an all-time low of 10 enrollees in 2022. Although recovering, the MAEd suffers the stiffest downward swerve compared to BEd and BEEd. The MAEd program hopes to have 40 students in the next school year if the upward trend continues. The latest enrollment is down by 57.4% compared to the 2019 record.

Figure 7. Enrollment Forecast for MAEd for the S.Y. 2024-2025

Figure 8. Enrollment Forecast for the Tertiary Level for the S.Y. 2024-2025

Overall, enrollment at the tertiary level experienced a 22.9% decrease during the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic. It recovered gradually the following year but experienced another decrease in 2022-2023. However, S.Y. 2023-2024 shows a promising upward trend for tertiary-level enrollment.

Getting the total of all enrollment data from different tertiary programs, an upward trend can be seen (Figure 8). The tertiary department hopes to have an enrollment from 690 students in S.Y. 2023-2024 to an estimated number of 900+ enrollees in S.Y. 2024-2025 at 86.46% variables correlation.

4 Conclusion and Recommendation

Almost all of the programs suffered a fall in enrollment during the COVID-19 pandemic. The resiliency in the number of enrollments can be seen in the BS in Information Technology and BS in Criminology programs which were not affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. They thrived despite the pressing conditions.

Swerving patterns can be seen in the graph of BSEd, BEEd, and BSBA but a stiff downfall is noticeable in the MAEd program. It is recommended that the pattern be investigated further since the swerving pattern can be seen in the College of Teacher Education. This can be attributed to several factors such as management style, marketing, and pedagogies, among others.

Overall, a promising outlook was forecasted. Despite the up-and-down trends, an estimated number of 900+ students can be expected at a confidence level of 86.46 percent of correlation between variables. It is therefore essential that planning should be done in anticipation of the said numbers. Institutional strategic and college-level planning is recommended.

References

- Hosler, D., & Shapiro, D. (2019). *Strategic Enrollment Management: Transforming Higher Education*. Jossey-Bass.
- Kim, Y., & Shin, E. (2020). A Forecasting Model for University Enrollment Management. *Sustainability*, 12(19), 8038.
- Lee, J., & Kang, M. (2021). Predictive Analytics for Student Success in Higher Education: A Systematic Literature Review. *Computers & Education*, 168, 104211.
- Sengupta, N. K., & Biswas, P. (2019). Financial Forecasting in Higher Education: A Case Study. *International Journal of Education Economics and Development*, 10(1), 53-73.
- Wiers-Jenssen, J., & Naevestad, T. O. (2019). Forecasting Student Enrollments in Higher Education: A Comparison of Statistical Models. *Higher Education*, 77(2), 231-248.